

The Architecture, Design and Justification of an Ontology-Based Business Vocabulary Assistant

Steven Hart

Department of Computer Science, Brunel University London

Abstract

This paper presents research into the business integration, software architecture, design and ontology for a business vocabulary assistant (BVA). The proposed application adopts an ontology framework to assist employees across an enterprise with the interpretation of documentation. The type of documentation in question is natural language, unstructured written entities, such as emails, technical specifications and project progress documents.

Employees within an enterprise work within divisions and departments which each communicate with a differing vocabulary. Departmental vocabularies develop over time to allow them to communicate efficiently within that department. When different business areas communicate with differing vocabularies and semantics, cross-department communications can become inefficient and frustrating. This research looks at how different business areas can be better integrated by interpreting written documentation.

The research initially assesses the problem space, confirmed through the testing of 49 subjects. It was found that providing additional information for complex, abbreviated and business-area-specific terminology improves the understanding of written documentation across a wide range of age groups, levels of industry experience and academic backgrounds. It was also ascertained, as initially predicted, that three types of problematic terms exist. A BVA solution would need to:

- Expand acronyms based on their origins; different departments can use the same acronym for a different expanded terminology.
- Enforce the use of an agreed business vocabulary by providing the author with synonyms for slang, misleading or non-words.
- Add an explanation to complex terms which may not be understood outside their department of origin.

In response to these findings, a solution in the form of a software architecture, design and ontology was developed. The architecture was proposed through substantial analysis of many academically and industrially recognised patterns and architectural designs. A systems overview and various UML diagrams were created during the architectural design element of this research. A prototype system was developed to further understand and support the architectural decisions. Potential technologies for adoption into a BVA were identified by actively experimenting with their functionality and critically analysing their suitability. Multiple potential ontology designs were developed and critically evaluated, and a final ontology model was produced. Its ability to provide a complete solution for users

dealing with complex, abbreviated and business-area-specific terminology was demonstrated through querying the ontology and evaluating the output.

All supporting code, ontology files and BVA test forms are available in the supplementary materials accompanying this paper. A prototype application demonstrating the core functionality was deployed at www.owl-bva.appspot.com, including a live version of the BVA test.

Keywords: ontology; OWL; business vocabulary; semantic web; natural language interpretation; enterprise architecture; design science research

Note: figures, diagrams, screenshots and code listings referenced in the text (e.g. Figure 1, Figure 4) are provided in the supplementary materials accompanying this submission.

Introduction

This paper presents research into the business integration, software architecture, and design of an ontology for a business vocabulary assistant (BVA). The proposed application adopts an ontology framework to assist enterprise employees with the interpretation of natural language written documentation, such as emails, technical specifications and progress reports. During the course of this research the author has worked within the engineering division of a large defence enterprise and the IT department of a claims management company. This provides significant insight into the industrial context of the problem and is reflected upon throughout the research.

Research Background

This section documents how this research fits in with current research and technologies. Primarily, this research concerns the use of ontology for the structuring and retrieval of information. The significance of using ontology for the development of BVA is that it presents major advantages over other approaches. Ontology concerns the 'explicit conceptualisation of a specification' (Gruber, 1993). It is used to represent objects within a domain and describes objects by representing the relationships they have with other objects, or classes of objects, within the domain. The relationship between two or more pieces of data can provide very useful information for IS development. Ontology is centred on a subject based classification, which has been a constituent part of information retrieval in libraries for many years in the form of subject taxonomy (Welty & Jenkins, 1999). The significance of work on IS libraries is that it identifies the need for subject based classification, which is required in this research to allow terms to be grouped into overlapping classes. Welty & Jenkins identify the online issue of information retrieval and discuss the impact of using ontology frameworks to elevate these issues early on in (Welty & Jenkins, 1999). The development of an ontology based BVA solution concerns the interpretation of natural language, an increasingly popular research area in the 2000s. This research area is discussed in depth in the literature review.

A significant element to this research concerns researching the design of a BVA and how it should interact with users. While a BVA is not a spell checker or thesaurus it is envisioned

to integrate with applications in a similar way to improve a user's experience. The computer spell checker and thesaurus was the first type of document consistency assistant, originally as standalone programs and relatively shortly after as part of word processing applications. The spell checker was theorised in literature as early as 1960 by the USA department of defence researcher, Charles Blair (Blair, 1960). But it was not till the 1980s that spell checkers became available within word processors on personal computers (Haswell, 2005). In the 1990s online versions of vocabulary consistency checkers began to become available. These online tools made it possible to find synonyms for words, expansions to acronyms and dictionaries that identify slang words. However, a business couldn't identify preferred synonyms; the expansions for acronyms usually contain many expansions, and often not the correct one for the author's acronym; the identification of slang words is only available on a limited amount of words, does not consider real words used in the wrong way or allow a business to identify words they don't want a particular department to use.

The Following timeline identifies the key points in history that vocabulary checkers have made a notable technological achievement.

Figure 1 Timeline of Semantic and vocabulary checkers

While this research is not a spell checker or a thesaurus; there are strong similarities between their existences. They both exist to assist a user writing or reading a written document.

Research Focus

The following section provides an academic and industrial rationale for the research. Within industry business terms used in many enterprises are not managed systematically; they are used implicitly without explicit definition, so that humans and systems are in difficulties for communication (Kang, Choi, Kim. 2010). Many business areas can function concurrently, which can lead to business areas to become isolated from one another over

time. The isolation of business areas leads to the arrival at disparate vocabularies and business area semantics. While business areas need to allow departments to use their respective vocabularies, cross divisional and managerial document understanding can suffer. The interpretation and analysis of natural language documents could provide an effective and efficient means for assisting users when reading such documentation. A primary concern of this research is evaluating whether a document can be made understandable by all employees within an organisation.

The BVA solution seeks to provide expansions to acronyms, explanations to complex terms and suggests replacements to slang and inappropriate terms. Providing additional information to a structured piece of text is fundamental to the study of ontology and evident in a significant number of practical applications, most significantly in academic journals from 2000 onwards. It will need to overcome the significant gap between knowledge expressed as textual documents and knowledge represented as ontologies (Eriksson, 2007). However, recent technological advancement such as Protégé 4 (Stanford University, 2009) and OWL 2 (W3C, 2009) has acted to reduce this gap considerably.

Aims and Objectives

The following section defines what the research is setting out to achieve, and the objectives it must meet to realise that aim. The aim of this research is to determine if an ontology based business vocabulary assistant is a suitable approach for interpreting natural language user written documents. It also needs to establish how to assist enterprise employees with understanding documentation as a precursor to this. The research explores an under-considered issue that is very predominant in industry. It aims to make the benefits of developing a business vocabulary assistant instantly recognisable and achievable.

The research has two main objectives that can be broken down further into more granular objectives. The initial objective is:

- Determine the types of problems the business vocabulary assistant can help with and the level of benefit that would be realised.
- Determine the types of business specific terminology users find unintelligible.
- Determine the severity of the issue across a range of experience and age groups.
- Synthesise the results and comments made by participants and use this information to guide completion of the second objective.

Once the way in which an assistant could help employees understand has been realised it will allow the second objective to be addressed. The second objective is:

- Realise the key development considerations of business vocabulary assistants through the construction of an architecture, design and basic prototype system for a business vocabulary assistant.
- Construct an architecture that could be used to develop an effective BVA.

- Review the currently available technologies when constructing the architecture and critically evaluate their usefulness for this application.
- Develop an ontology that demonstrates that a range of business specific terms can be expanded / explained efficiently.
- Develop a basic prototype system that can be referenced throughout the document to support research findings.

The next section is the literature review. This in-depth study of the currently available literature in the relevant research areas is essential for guiding and informing this piece of research.

Literature Review

The literature review critically evaluates the key journal articles that are in the areas of research that this research is in. It should help demonstrate that this work is required and has not been addressed previously.

The theoretical aspects of ontology in IS development is a well discussed research area. Over the past few years more papers have focused on the practical application of ontology, however journals specifically on the area of business vocabulary conformity checking are limited. However, a significant number of journals briefly discuss the topic area or carry out similar theoretical research or development projects. Literature that discusses the use of the Web Ontology Language and the Protégé tool are of particular interest, however the review also includes examples of literature that have approached the problem differently where appropriate.

Literature Researched

The follow section documents the literature researched during the course of the literature review. Literature concerning the theoretical application of ontology and the reasons for an ontological approach to a problem provide a basis for justifying the initial and high level architecture and design choices. A key article by Eriksson (2007) looks at how semantic documents can be created from ontologies and their textural counterparts, natural language documents. The problem is fundamentally similar to this research, with regards to the analysis and interpretation of documentation. In addition, Nesic et al. (2008) conducts some research that complements Eriksson (2007) by discussing a similar problem but gearing the research more towards the management of semantic documents. This research will provide useful organisation / management guidance for the BVA ontology. The problematic issue of ambiguity of terminology in large scale ontology systems is apparent in the two previously discussed journals. Welty and Jenkins (1999) researches this area in depth, providing invaluable guidance for recreating the type of ambiguous terminology that will need to be present in this research test data. A more recent, complementary piece of research by Guo and Zhang (2009) presents an OWL based pervasive agent ontology for semantic information integration. Again, this research will help guide develop a BVA

ontology that is considerate of the multiple meaning terminology issues that will be faced by this research. Another approach to the problem is made by Bobillo et al. (2009) who combine an OWL ontology and fuzzy logic model to try and overcome the problems involved with attempting computer interpretation of vast natural language vocabularies.

A consideration of the architecture and design of the BVA application is adoption and reuse throughout the business. Simperl (2009) conducts two detailed case studies in the areas of eHealth and eRecruitment. The case studies specifically concern the issues of ontology reuse on the semantic web. These case studies will provide much insight for the architecture and design of the BVA application. Harnessing the distribution and reuse advantages of the semantic web are further discussed by García-Sánchez et al. (2009). They look at how parts of a knowledge domain could be populated by intelligent agents which gather segments of the vocabulary through semantic web services. This framework could guide the integration of a BVA application with the semantic web. The research by Brasethvik and Gulla (2001) is similar; however it focuses more on how such a framework can be implemented and how it would be possible to deliver the gathered segments of information to the end user. Another deployment concern of the BVA application is the large scale realisation of a BVA application. While the proof of concept ontology is small enough to be handled by a conventional OWL reasoner the architecture shall be aware of the fact that current reasoners cannot handle large ontologies and are liable to crash. A solution that adopts relational databases is presented by Al-Jadir et al. (2010) and will guide development in this area significantly. In addition to this, the research carried out by Motik et al. (2009) discusses the differences between relational databases and OWL and the logic union between the two. This will also be useful for guiding the architecture and design in this area. Consideration on how a relational database can be used in conjunction with an ontology to organise data into domain knowledge, as suggested in Ranganathan & Liu (2006) will also be made.

When interpreting acronyms the BVA ontology is expected to present intelligent results to the user and not just lists of possibilities which do little to guide the user towards the correct explanation of an acronym. A possibility for managing this complexity is to separate domain knowledge and operational knowledge. Shue et al. (2009) present an interesting method of using Protégé for domain knowledge and Jess for operational knowledge.

Gruber (1993) is a significant piece of research that has been cited in other research in the field frequently. It clearly and concisely documents the requirement for the sharing and reuse of formally represent knowledge for AI systems. The design choices made by Gruber in defining an ontology framework are inspirational and will guide the BVA ontology development during the proof of concept stages. A complimentary piece of research by Kang et al. (2010) provides a novel and innovative approach to building enterprise architecture with ontology. The findings in their article could provide valuable justification for the suitability of ontology for enterprise scale systems over other methods. This would primarily support the design of the proposed BVA application with regards to its scalability. Another key approach to ontology based systems architecture is presented by Kiyavitskaya et al. (2009), who develop CERNO, a tool for semantic annotation of text documents. The semantic models they present provide valuable insight into how a complex vocabulary can be broken down using hierarchical structures and then by ontologies. This is an interesting

approach which combines two fundamentally different approaches to solve a similar problem to the one faced by this research. A piece of research with similarities in this context is presented by Yang et al. (2009), who present a useful piece of research into product configuration modelling using OWL, SWRL and JESS. The research documents an actual implementation of a product configuration modelling system that will be useful in guiding the development of the BVA application proof of concept.

It is recognised that building ontologies manually can be a labour intensive task; a strong enterprise deployment consideration of this research is how this process could be sped up. Brewster et al. (2009) present a method for training an ontology that will be considered when discussing these kinds of deployment issues with business vocabulary assistants. A good example of the effort involved is apparent in Dill et al. (2003) who document a large scale semantic tagging effort made in 2003. The issues encountered are indicative of the ones that face the realisation of a BVA application. It also provides a concise overview of existing technologies and literature that will prove invaluable in guiding the BVA application design. The next step of development after design would encompass implementing the application. The Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM) presented in (Djurić et al. 2005) allows ontology based systems to be created with a model driven architecture approach, which may be useful in the development of a BVA.

Solutions to conceptually similar problem spaces through different approaches provide a useful way to highlight the limitations of the OWL / ontology approach. Bada and Hunter (2010) present an insight into the difficulties faced with semantic annotation of biomedical documents. While this research will not be dealing with biomedical terminology it is conceptually similar as an instance of a technical vocabulary. This in depth account of the attempts and collaborations made to solve semantic interpretation of biomedical documentation provides valuable insight into how this research can address the issues of interpreting business vocabulary semantics. Another notable research within biomedical informatics was made by Brennan and Aronson (2003) who try to interpret emails sent by patients to doctors to assist them in diagnosing the patient's condition. The difficulties faced here will be similar to the difficulties of exchanging documentation between technical and non-technical staff in the business, as faced by the BVA solution. In addition to Brennan and Aronson (2003) the research by Trappey et al. (2009) presents a method for interpreting doctor's notes / emails for patient summarisation and categorisation that will provide insight into the natural language interpretation issues faced by this research. The issue of selecting the correct term across multiple vocabularies, such as the BVA ontologies divisional vocabularies is a difficult subject area. Gray et al. (2010) present a very promising investigation of selection across astronomical vocabularies using term weighting. This could aid the implementation of the sentence analysis required to be done by the BVA. Ma et al. (2010) presents an approach to making a Chinese mining enterprise semantically interoperable by adopting a business vocabulary that gathers terms from geosciences taxonomies and terminologies. Conceptually it is one of the most similar case studies to this piece of research although the approach differs significantly. It will be useful to draw comparisons between the approaches throughout the research. It also discusses classification based on an accuracy rating which may be required by this research.

Literature Review Conclusion

The literature review has critically evaluated research that has significant similarities with this research. The articles discussed loosely fit into three categories, firstly, the theoretical application of ontology in applications with a natural language interpretation element. Secondly, the architecture, design and deployment of ontology based solutions with a natural language interpretation element. Finally, different approaches to conceptually similar problem spaces, for approach reflection. The following section, Methodology, discusses how this research meets the individual objectives by defining which techniques, data and methods were used to answer each of them.

Methodology

This section looks at how this research meets the two objectives set out in the Introduction, by defining which techniques, data and methods were used to answer each of them. The following diagram is the research design overview. It displays the order in which the key research tasks will be undertaken.

Figure 2 research design overview

Data Gathering Methodology (Objective One)

Objective one precedes the main body of work (objective two) and aims to theorise the benefits of BVA deployment to an enterprise. It is the methodology for meeting the first objective set out in the Introduction. Undertaking this research will help to reduce the complexity of objective two research which is important because designing useful artefacts is complex due to the need for creative advances in domain areas in which existing theory is often insufficient (Hevner et al. 2004).

Build

The build section looks at the considerations for constructing a reliable and accurate test. Documentation originating from multiple enterprise divisions is potentially not understood by everyone within all enterprise divisions. Analysis of enterprise documentation has identified three types of problematic terminology:

- Unexpanded acronyms.
- Slang, misleading or non-words.
- Complex or technical terms.

A test will need to be constructed to identify which of these three categories of business terminology cause employees a problem and the scale of the problem. The test should gain demographic information, test the participants' underlying knowledge, then gauge their improvement after exposure to BVA correct text. The follow diagram demonstrates how the test will be structured:

Figure 3 BVA Test Structure

Each box represents a form. If the structure is not apparent, visit the live test at www.owl-bva.appspot.com/BVA-Test-Redirect.html (see supplementary materials).

The requirements for the model are as follows:

- The Passages need to be long enough to include multiple instances of business specific terminology but not so many that the participant loses interest.
- The passages need to originate from multiple different business divisions.
- The participants' underlying knowledge will need to be ascertained.
- The participant's knowledge after reading the BVA adjusted passages will need to be ascertained.

- The passages will need to be tested on a range of participants of significant enterprise-meaningful diversity.
- The participant will need to be explained the rules and guidelines, it must also be ensured they adhere to the rules.
- The participant’s views on the test will need to be ascertained to ensure that issues have not been overlooked.
- The passages of text will need to at least reflect real passages of text from an enterprise.

It is considered that 20-30 minutes is a realistic time to expect a participant to stay focused and complete the test without deferring. The passages will originate from three business areas; sales / marketing, Engineering and IT, this should provide a wide enough impression of an enterprise without overwhelming the test participant. This allows for 200-300 word passages, large enough to contain approximately 8 problematic terms. Each passage, correct and uncorrected, will be preceded by 4 questions. The following table estimates the test completion time.

Table 1 Test Time Breakdown

Element	Time (slow)	Time(Fast)
Pre-questions	3	2
Text passages – set 1	6	4
Questions – set 1	4.5	3
Text passages – set 2	6	4
Questions – set 2	4.5	3
Post-Questions	6	2
Totals	30	18

To gauge the participants' underlying knowledge the first three uncorrected passages have questions about them that the participant would only know if they had previous exposure to the terminology in question. The corrected three passages will have questions about them similar to the first set of questions, but not the same. The passages are not after each other to avoid the effects of simultaneous digestion of information, as displayed above in Figure 3. The identified corrections are listed below.

Table 2 Sales and Marketing Passage Adjustments

ID	Required Change	Notes
1	Tangible products should be products you can physically touch	The ‘tangible products’ term is sales slang and may not make a lot of sense to a lot of people

ID	Required Change	Notes
2	First instance of PSS should be Professional Selling Skills (PPS)	
3	Canvassing should be cold calling	Canvassing is not part of the business vocabulary
4	First Instance of A&P should be advertising and promotion (A&P)	
5	First Instance of B2B should be Business to Business (B2B)	
6	First instance of lead time should be lead time (time between order and provision of goods or service)	Also needs to detect lead-time
7	Target should be sales target	Possible conflict with other uses of target such as target audience
8	Q2 should be 2nd Quarter	Q2 is Slang that is not in the business vocabulary

Table 3 Engineering Passage Adjustments

ID	Required Change	Notes
1	First instance of UAV needs to be Unmanned Air Vehicle (<i>UAV</i>)	
2	The first instance of Sortie needs to have an explanation. Sortie (<i>The period the UAV is in the air</i>)	Needs to take into account the plural s after sortie (sorties)
3	The first instance of Serial needs to have an explanation. Serial (<i>A planned sequence of events</i>)	
4	Algo team should be Algorithms (Calculation, Data Processing and Mathematical reasoning) team	All instances need changing as it is a slang term but only the first instant needs explanation.

ID	Required Change	Notes
5	SW should be Software	All instances need changing as it is a slang term.
6	First instance of SW should be SW (<i>South West</i>)	Manage conflict with Software slang SW
7	Evading engagement needs to have an explanation. Evading engagement (<i>moving away from hostile threat</i>)	
8	First instance of PIIPs needs to be Product Integration and Installation Plan (<i>PIIPs</i>)	
9	Exec should be Executive	Possible conflict with execution. All instances need changing as it is a slang term.

Table 4 IT Passage Adjustments

ID	Required Change	Notes
1	First Instance of VoIP should be Voice over IP (Internet Telephone System)	
2	First Instance of Active Directory should be Active Directory (Users and Access Manager)	
3	First Instance of Bridge should be bridge (Connection between two networks)	Possible conflict with the primary use of the word bridge.
4	First instance of LAN should be Local Area Network (LAN)	
5	network switches should be network switches(Connects segments of the computer network)	Will need to deal with plural (switch, Switches)
6	Bottlenecking should be bottlenecking (point at	

ID	Required Change	Notes
	which the flow of data is most highly restricted)	
7	MTA should be Message Transfer Agent (MTA)	
8	SMTP should be Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP)	
9	VPN should be Virtual Private Network (VPN – used to connect from home computers)	

Distributing the test to approximately 50 participants will allow for a wide range of age, sex, background and experience to be tested. The Pre-test questions ensure participants come from a variety of age, sex, background and experience. The test is monitored to eliminate chances of participants cheating with search engines, web resources and caching / revisiting forms. Time limits are not in place as this may frustrate users and adversely affect results accuracy by rushing users into picking a decision without thinking things through. The participant is given the chance to add comments on what could be done to improve clarity and any issues or feelings they had on the test. To ensure realistic passages of text are presented, the first instance of each text is a real passage of text that has been published within the business. However it may have had irrelevant and sensitive parts removed. Tests will need to be administered in a non-hostile, usual environment, reflective of the work environment that a BVA would be deployed in where possible. Ideally, participants will take the test at their desk computers / own environment to limit the effects of the participant's daily patterns of work disturbance as this may adversely affect the accuracy of the results.

Evaluation

The evaluation section looks at how the data will need to be organised to best support the appraisal of the testing exercise. Primarily, the increased level of understanding will need to be ascertained and ultimately whether the participant understanding increase is significant enough to justify the second phase of research. The factors that improvement will be gauged against are age, experience and terminology type. This will demonstrate the user groups who the BVA could benefit most significantly and what types of terminology the BVA will need to assist with. The data is dissected by six age groups (<20, 20-30, 31-40, 41-50, 51-60 and >60). Experience is organised into the following groups:

Table 5 Experience Grouping

Group Name	Definition
Inexperienced Participant	The participant has not studied or worked in any of the disciplines being tested

Group Name	Definition
Single discipline Education	The participant has studied in one discipline
Multidiscipline Education	The participant has studied in more than one discipline
Single discipline industry experience	The participant has worked in one discipline
multidiscipline industry experience	The participant has worked in multiple disciplines
Single discipline education and experience	The participant has worked in one discipline and also studied in one discipline
Multi discipline education and experience	The participant has worked and studied in multiple disciplines.

The data will need to be synthesised into graphs and discussed in the findings chapter. The graphs will need to be clear. To achieve this, the graphs for age and experience will be plotted separately with clearly labelled axis. Terminology type improvement will be in a simple table displaying improvement averages for each type.

Theory

The following results predictions are made:

- Less experienced participants will make a more significant score improvement between uncorrected and corrected passages than those with more experience.
- The corrected passage results should be fairly constant among all experience groups.
- The proposed three types of problematic terminology would have caused the majority of participants significant understanding difficulty.

Data Justification

Unforeseen issues could arise during testing that means the results are less accurate than expected. Should any unforeseen issues arise they will be documented. If the issue invalidates the data it will need to be discarded, the problem rectified and new participants tested.

Methodology framework adapted from (March & Smith, 1995).

Architecture, Design and Ontology Methodology (Objective 2)

This section looks at how the second objective will be met. Guided by the results of the first phase of research the second phase will be:

Realise the key development considerations of business vocabulary assistants through the construction of an architecture and design for a business vocabulary assistant.

Problem Identification

There is no automated solution to assist with the explanation and expansion of business area language. As demonstrated in the findings of research phase one this causes employees to have a reduced understanding of certain business areas.

Motivation

Employees with a reduced understanding of the business operations outside of their own division can become isolated from the enterprises overall goals. It also limits the potential for redeployment of employees as they are not learning the key principles of their colleagues' work.

Definition of Solution Objective

The solution needs to consist of an architectural design that could be realised if it was to be developed in the future. To demonstrate the viability of the architecture a simple prototype application shall be developed to demonstrate the core functionality. The solution also needs to include an ontology model that responds correctly when passed queries from within the prototype application and the protégé DL-Query tab. In order to justify and evaluate the architectural choices a basic prototype system will be developed.

Design

Design is both a process and a product (Hevner et al. 2004). The following points identify the process that must be followed to deliver the architecture, design and ontology, which is the product. The design needs to undertake the following tasks:

- An Architectural Design for a generic BVA solution, critically evaluating:
 - The requirements, through system use cases
 - The High level architecture
 - Consideration of the application Interface
 - Consideration of existing, reusable technologies
 - Exploration of maintenance and developer usage
 - A class diagram that adopts researched architectural patterns
- An Ontology for a generic BVA solution, that demonstrates:
 - A design model that works when presented with queries
 - A design that is workable, with regards to amount of maintenance and effort to keep it operational

- A design that utilises the functionality of OWL effectively.

Demonstration

The architectural design will be realised by a final class diagram, demonstrating the architecture can be used to assist the creation of a class diagram. The core functionality of the architectural design will also be demonstrated by developing a simple prototype system. The ontology will be demonstrated with screen shots documenting the behaviour of the system when passed queries. These will be in the form of scenarios indicative of real world scenarios.

Evaluation

The research will evaluate the findings by assessing them against the following evaluation criteria:

- Evaluate whether an ontology approach is a suitable approach for a BVA application.
- Evaluate types of application deployment that would assist in realising the full potential of a BVA solution
- Evaluate the currently available technologies that could assist in realising the full potential of a BVA solution
- Create a class diagram which can be evaluated by the development of a prototype system which utilises it
- Evaluate the Ontology design process by developing an ontology and testing its robustness with DL-queries
- Evaluate the Ontology design by testing it with queries that assess its performance when presented with differing linguistic rules and semantics
- Evaluate the performance of the prototype system by running test scenarios which evaluate whether the solution can provide meaning for acronyms, complex terminology and slang terms.

Academic journals will assist in evaluating the findings throughout.

Methodology framework adapted from (Peffer et al. 2008).

Ethical Considerations

References will be made where work has been cited to acknowledge the author's work. These citations will be a true representation of the author's work.

The following activities will not occur under any circumstance:

- Fabrication of Data
- Falsification of Data through omission or editing

- Citing literature that does not exist
- Plagiarism of any kind
- Company confidential and sensitive material will not be released (the text passages in use have been vetted and approved for any use)

Participants consent to taking the test as an optional activity and are not pushed or persuaded if they express a wish not to be involved. Participants have a right to withdraw from the test while it is taking place, once submitted the test data is anonymous so cannot be removed. Individuals that have been interviewed during the course of the research maintain the right to be excluded, and if they are cited in the text it will not divulge their name or any other personal information. They were also given the chance to review the citation and exercise their right to be excluded before the research was finalised. Tests will be conducted in accordance with the environment's health and safety guidelines. Test Results will be made available to test participants once all tests have been conducted.

Methodology Conclusion

The Methodology section documented the approach taken in meeting the aims and objectives of the research. It presented an approach which consists of two main sections. Firstly, a data gathering exercise which aims to assess the scale and nature of the problem space. Secondly, it documents the approach that will be taken in order to develop the architecture, design, ontology and prototype system. The following section documents the data gathering exercise. It synthesises data collected from testing 49 participants and discusses the results it presents.

Data Gathering (Objective 1)

The following section synthesises the results of the test data gathering exercise. The full results data set is available in the supplementary materials accompanying this paper. 49 applicants from a range of disciplines, education and age groups were selected to take a test to gauge the potential performance of a deployed BVA solution. The test definition and rationale are presented in the Data Gathering Methodology section above, with full materials available in the supplementary files accompanying this paper.

Objective 1 Findings

The initial dissection of data involved analysing the age groups of participants and the average performances of that age group.

Figure 4 performance based on age groups

With regards to the age groups the general trend was that the younger audiences generally had a similar or slightly higher increase in performance between the passages of text compared to the older groups. This slightly differs from the prediction that younger age groups would have a significantly higher increase due to having a lower fundamental knowledge and taking in information more effectively. It may be the case that experience is a more important factor than age.

Evaluating the improvement based on experience reveals that the general pattern is, as initially predicted, that the solution would bring all experience level groups towards a similar performance rating on the second (corrected by BVA) passages.

Figure 5 Performance increase across all age groups, by experience group

Those with less experience generally had a lower first score than those with more experience. The performance results on the second passage of text (the one corrected by the checker) confirmed that the BVA corrections had made a significant increase in performance, most noticeably in less experienced groups. This demonstration is of interest to determine its industrial applications. Increasing specialization and complexity of companies has given rise to the necessity of an integral management of own resources (Bobillo et al. 2009). The BVA provides a working business integration tool necessitated by increasing business complexity.

Both graphs demonstrate a high level of improvement in all participant groups. Out of the 49 participants 37 improved, 10 had the same score and 2 had a reduced score. Looking at the comments made about the test there it would appear that the second version was too lengthy and there was a temptation to skim read it (which may explain the same score and reduced score results) as the subject matter had already been read about previously. If this is the case the improvement figures should be considered modest due to the limitations of the testing structure.

The results demonstrate that the three originally proposed problem areas all cause significant understanding difficulties. The Following table displays the average improvement made

Table 6 Score improvement between uncorrected and corrected text passages questions

Type	Uncorrected Passage Average	Corrected Passage Average
Slang, Misleading or Non-Words	47.6%	78.6%
Acronyms	69%	84.2%
Complex Terminology	58.2%	72.4%

Therefore a BVA solution will need to:

- Expand acronyms based on their origins; different departments can use the same acronym for a different expanded terminology.
- Enforce the use of an agreed business vocabulary by providing the author with synonyms for slang, misleading or non-words.
- Add an explanation to complex terms which may not be understood outside their department of origin.

These three points are the fundamental requirements of a BVA solution. The following chapter evaluates the findings documented in this chapter and how it supports the justification of the development of a BVA architecture, design and ontology.

Objective 1 Evaluation

The following section concisely evaluates the findings of the previous section. A BVA can theoretically provide a useful solution within an enterprise to assist with the consumption of natural language documentation. The BVA would be most useful for new starts and junior staff who would benefit from an increased understanding of the enterprise's business. Interestingly it was found that more experienced staff could also benefit by using the system to clarify terms. It was also ascertained that delivering additional information about terms participants understood frustrated them and as such a better method of presenting additional information should be a key consideration in objective 2. Some comments suggested that the questions were frustrating as the answers were not present in the respective passages, this acts to further enforce the justification of the BVA as this was the primary reason for its conceptualisation.

During the construction of the test data it was realised that many terms have equivalent ways of expressing a term using different terminology. It was also uncovered that certain terms can exist in more than one vocabulary. These types of issues are particularly suited to ontology based systems, which is discussed in the following section. The following section, objective 2 findings, discusses possible approaches to the problem that utilise ontology. It also compares the ontology approach to other possible approaches and justifies why this approach has been taken.

Architecture, Design and Ontology Findings (Objective 2)

The following section discusses the most central aspect of the research. It critically evaluates the use of ontology for a BVA solution, the proposed architecture, design, ontology and prototype system. Current technologies associated with the study of ontology have been researched and evaluated with the assistance of relevant academic journals.

The Application

The following section introduces the application and the reasoning behind the architecture and design choices. Specifically it critically evaluates the choice of ontology for the BVA. Adopting an ontology approach to developing a BVA presents the developer with many key advantages over other types of implementation. The construction of an ontology allows an ontology reasoner to infer additional information based on the existing asserted knowledge. When made contextually relevant to a user's problem by the initiation of a query this inference can intelligently assist a user. An interesting application of this is the Amazon Ontology (Benson & Battle, 2007) which uses an ontology reasoner to infer publications it envisages a user may be interested in. A conceptually similar application could be made by a BVA. If integrated with the employee's grade and department it could determine which complex terms require expansion and how much expansion is required. The BVA ontology could be connected to the FOAF (Friend of a friend) and SIOC (Semantically interlinked On-Line Community) ontologies to formally represent user profiles (Nesic et al. 2008). A different approach to this problem would be the use of mathematical models, in which each potentially related expansion is given a score based on various criteria that indicate relevance. The highest scoring expansion is presented first to the user. The problem with this approach is that it is often very time consuming, complex to implement and not necessarily user specific. In addition making adjustments after the initial implementation can be difficult as adjusting the scoring to change one outcome can inadvertently change another calculation making it incorrect. An approach with qualities from both of the two previously discussed would be to adopt an ontology agent such as AgentOWL, which could assist with returning more accurate results by observing and imitating users. (Fu et al. 2008). The use of intelligent agents should be considered as a future enhancement for a complex BVA solution.

The use of ontology and specifically OWL ontology promotes reuse on the web. An application such as a BVA may use multiple ontologies, some very specific to its operation and others that have been adopted from other projects who developed them for multiple applications. Consider how, due to the complexity of the English language, many of the terms in the BVA test data had multiple forms. For example the key word serial could appear as serials or the key word 'bottlenecking' could have appeared as 'bottleneck'. Rather than defining all of these forms an ontology project which defines English terms could be used. The WordNet (Princeton University, 2011) is an ontology database which could use basic terms to interpret business descriptions (Culley & Darlington. 2008). There are several issues with this approach. A business operates a differing and sometimes contradicting vocabulary / semantics to that of everyday English language. Secondly a

business uses many slang words and acronyms that do not feature in everyday English. Although ultimately they could be added to an instance of WordNet, care would have to be taken to not adopt too rich a functionality set and make adding additional terms to the BVA too labour intensive for users to tolerate.

A BVA ontology should ideally only contain information relevant to the domain and information that is required for its operation. The use of ontology allows a developer to separate out domain knowledge from operational knowledge. This allows a knowledgeable expert to define the underlying domain without thinking about the processes required for that domain knowledge to be true. For example the GOLD ontology (GOLD Community, 2010) allows a user to model words and builds up an understanding of how they are expressed in the English language. The modelling of this domain knowledge does not need to be operationally defined; it is simply considered true within the context of the domain. Operational knowledge would overcomplicate the ontology, provide little benefit for the adopting application and would limit its reusability. A relational database structure can contain data specific to a domain but cannot organise it into knowledge without a software domain logic layer (which usually organises operational knowledge into classes) or ontology (which organises domain knowledge into classes). A common approach is to store data in a relational database and domain knowledge in ontologies, As Ranganathan & Liu (2006) did to return semantically relevant results to a user's query. The GOLD ontology is very complex and populating it with business terms has been deemed too expansive for the prototype BVA solution to adopt efficiently. While adopting developed ontologies can reduce overall development time, ontologies that are too complex for their desired purpose can impose additional complexity to the underlying domain logic and increase development time.

The organisation of domain knowledge with ontology allows a very human friendly way to interact with the information. Especially with OWL / ontology development tools such as Protégé that adopt a very visual approach to ontology development. This proved particularly useful, arriving at the best design for the BVA ontology, which took many iterative cycles, discussed later in this section. In addition to this studying the ontology from within Protégé assisted development of the prototype systems domain logic, aiding the navigation of its structure. OWL is based on description logic, which enables automatic reasoning about inconsistency of knowledge bases and avoids terminological ambiguity. (Yang et al. 2009). Protégé visualises reasoner inferencing, highlighting additional relationships on the BVA ontologies modelled terms. This is useful when constructing an OWL-API data factory at a code level.

The construction of ontologies is, by definition, explicit. It is not an epistemology, in which multiple theories can be expressed. The explicit conceptualisation of a domain allows for a singular point of reference, minimising the risk of adopters misunderstanding a domain due to multiple theories existing within it. This maximises reuse among groups that share a common interest / understanding of a domain. As a future enhancement the BVA could be deployed as an online collaboration project in which groups could build vocabularies as they go, and integrate with websites that operate with technical vocabularies in order to expand and explain the resource to visitors. Different groups may adopt the online BVA project instead of deploying a solution to their website or company intranet, meaning they

save time and effort as they don't have to build a solution from scratch. Further to this, information processed by the BVA would be well suited for structuring into machine interpretable information for integration with the semantic web. This would not be possible without correctly connecting the BVA ontologies with external ontologies as automated agents would retrieve mismatched information.

Architecture and Design

The Architecture and Design section documents what architectural patterns will be adopted and the proposed design for the BVA. This section will also include UML diagrams for the purpose of guiding the implementation of a BVA. This research considers that software architecture is, fundamentally, a composition of architectural design decisions.' (Bosch, 2004)

The development of software systems can be assisted by model driven architecture (MDA) tools. However, currently available MDA tools have limited support for this functionality. Should MDA functionality be required the Jena Rule language is particularly amenable to transforming between Meta-Object Facility based modelling languages to an equivalent RDF representation (Cranfield & Pan. 2007). Conversion to a RDF representation could allow a user to export from a MDA tool and this would allow them to build the ontology framework based on the system classes. The Ontology Definition Metamodel approach presented by (Djurić et al. 2005) could be utilised as it has been developed in OWL. However it is thought that the size and scope of the majority of BVA implementations probably does not warrant the time it would take to develop this automation; unless the applications functionality was planned to expand rapidly. For this reason, the architecture is presented in a textual and diagrammatic form.

System Use Case

The following section looks at the potential user requirements of the system. The following diagram displays the use cases from an architectural level perspective.

Figure 6 SUC for a business vocabulary assistant

The use case diagram above is fairly generic, simply mapping the BVA goals as high level system requirements. In addition to this a development specific use case diagram will help to guide the development of a BVA. The following use case gives an example of a design level use case diagram.

Figure 7 SUC examples for a business vocabulary assistant

The use case diagram above demonstrates some example use cases that enterprise users may require from a BVA when deployed in an enterprise.

High Level Architecture

The high level architecture organises the main system components into layers, to better control the organisation of the applications implementation. A three layer application architecture approach is proposed with the presentation layer on the client tier and the domain logic and data source on a server tier. The terms tier and layer are not considered synonymous here. Tier implies a physical separation where as layer does not (Fowler, 2003).

Figure 8 business vocabulary assistant High Level Architecture

The client / server approach allows the system to remain flexible and easily distributable, the main reasons for this approach are:

- Allows the use of thin clients
- Single database for all users, alleviating version updating issues
- Single server configuration minimises OS / compatibility issues
- Adopts browser technology which is widely available and platform independent
- Allows the use of browser technologies for the presentation layer. Giving access to a powerful and vast range of interface controls.

A solution that allows a user to download the entire application to a client machine is undesirable for this application. The delivery of the solution via a client / server approach would allow the solution to be developed into a web services application, allowing the BVA to be offered as a service or it to be integrated into applications on remote computing systems. If the BVA was offered as a web service / resource aspects of the web service such as discovery, execution, selection, composition and interoperation may need to be automated due to the size and diversity of the internet (García-Sánchez et al. 2009).

Application interface

The application interface is an important consideration of the BVA. It provides the interface between the user interaction between the input / output devices and the rest of the system. How the user interface is presented can determine the success of a system.

Consideration of architectural patterns can assist the design of the user interface and help guide its deployment. The model view controller pattern presented by Fowler (2003) allows for multiple different views on multiple different devices. This would be useful for a BVA as it will need to be deployed differently for different users (power users, developers, authors and readers). It will also need to be deployed differently for different devices (web interface, word processor plug-in, mobile email client).

Figure 9 the Model View Controller Pattern (Fowler, 2003)

The controller takes user input and refers it to the model for processing. The View outputs the results of the referral back to the user. In the BVA the controller would very often be taking in text typed by a user and forming it into a query to execute on the reasoned ontology. Once the results have been returned to the domain logic they would be sent to the View. The view could present the results in many ways. For example it may present them in a similar way to a spell checking solution that highlights issues by underlining them. When the user right clicks on them the solution is presented. A toolkit for the implementation of interface objects such as the Google web toolkit would provide a developer with the means to create the view and controller components if this was required. Java is considered the best language choice as this is used by the majority of the OWL based projects currently available.

Architectural patterns that focus on minimising calls to the model reducing network traffic. It would not need to be an advanced solution, the nature of the BVA is to improve a users understanding of a document. It is not to analyse a large amount of documents automatically. For this reason patterns such as the data transfer object, which batches requests from multiple objects into a single remote call may be too complex a solution. Patterns such as the Remote Façade would minimise calls between the controller and the model. This is especially important if network traffic has to be minimised due to a very large scale deployment of a BVA.

Many of the comments made by test participants on which passage was easier to interpret suggested that the second instance of each passage of text was too long and wordy. The

basic Google documents questionnaire builder that was used to build the questionnaire only allowed the data to be presented in a fairly primitive way. The prototype solution demonstrates the use of JavaScript to create hover boxes for the user. It gives them a brief explanation and can also link to an information resource on the internet. The figure below demonstrates this functionality.

Figure 10 Prototype Implementation demonstrating textual analysis

A future development could be for the system to integrate into a browser like a spell checker and underline terms when they are discovered, allowing the user to right click and correct them like spelling mistakes. However, this would limit the application to browsers that support this functionality. The following diagram is a mock up of the right click functionality:

Users can communicate over the VoIP system.

Right Click Causes
Menu to Open in the
web interface

Figure 11 A complex acronym displays the user an expansion and an explanation

With basic spell checking the call to a dictionary lookup can be initiated when the space bar is pressed, causing a controller to send the string between the two previous spaces. With the business vocabulary checker this is more difficult. The terms it deals with are often more than one word. The prototype solution posts the form data when the user presses a submit button, limiting the server calls to one. However delivering this asynchronously could significantly increase server calls. The call to the domain logic could be made after every sentence as terms should not exist over two sentences. This could present a problem with overloading the server, asynchronously sending a call to the server after every sentence is not ideal because it would result in the domain logic having to query large arrays of data properties looking for textual matches after every sentence. The following UI design is a combination of the prototype solution and the right click spelling checking style of control.

Figure 12 How the user could call the analysis of a term

This method would mean that use of terms not in the business vocabulary would not be highlighted and would be the responsibility of the user to check. However it would not inconvenience the user with lots of highlighting on terms they already understand. If a BVA was deployed to an enterprise the best UI solution may be more obvious; most software engineering projects reveal that a large number of usability related requests are made after deployment (Balan & Punithavalli, 2010).

Prototype Implementation

Term Finder

The Term Finder looks for exact textual matches in the ontology. It does not return partial matches or rank returned terms in best match order. As discussed in the main dissertation document these things have been identified as future enhancements. to analyse a passage of text look on the analyse text page

Please Input Term:

Please Select Department Name:

Result Set 1 for UAV

Form Type	Form Value
Singular Form	unmanned air vehicle
Plural	unmanned air vehicles
Acronym	uav
Explanation	an air vehicle that can operate without having a pilot on board

Figure 13 Term finder prototype implementation

Query Input

The following section discusses a basic query input for experienced users and developers to interact with the ontology using queries. DL-Queries are made based on the concept, properties and instances defined in the ontology and return semantically relevant results (Ranganathan & Liu. 2006). In terms of potential patterns to realise query input, the Model View Controller might be a bit too complex a solution. The page controller pattern presented by Fowler (2003) is similar to the MVC pattern but is designed to be adopted to guide single page implementations where the page is deployed as a script (a java servlet page would be an effective way to deploy the query input) for the user to interact with.

Figure 14 the Page Controller Pattern (Fowler, 2003)

Page controllers are good for deploying a simple solution like this one. If the query input had more navigational complexity the front controller (Fowler, 2003), which manages a web page with a handler and a hierarchy of commands could be considered.

The type of query syntax used depends on the reasoner that is chosen. The Pellet reasoner for example, accepts queries in SPARQL and OWL-DL. A developed query input solution could be utilised. The tool ViziQuer (ViziQuer, 2010) for example, allows the graphical construction of SPARQL queries.

Figure 15 (ViziQuer, 2010) allows a user to build a query graphically

Using the ViziQuer solution could reduce development time of a business vocabulary solution. However, it would limit the user to SPARQL and the functionality set provided by the tool.

OWL Technologies and Reasoners

The following section discusses the reasons for using the OWL-API, OWL-DB and pellet reasoner in the BVA solution architecture. Due to its maturity and extensive functionality set, OWL-API reduced prototype deployment time considerably. The OWL API was developed as part of the CO ODE project and is a vital part in the architecture as it integrates all the other systems components allowing them to communicate. Alternatives to the OWL-API were considered. The Jena semantic web framework is similar however, persistence storage and rule based inference engine are built in, which may reduce deployment time at the expense of the OWL-APIs more flexible component driven architecture. For example, at time of writing the built in Jena reasoner does not have full OWL-DL support although the documentation describes how to implement the Pellet reasoner which does. The prototype system found the OWL-API to integrate seamlessly with the pellet reasoner and provides detailed java-docs for the majority of classes.

The ontology reasoner allows queries (by either the domain model or the query Input interface) to be made on a fully inferred model. Inferred relationships are the ones that the reasoner has calculated, based on the relationships and information asserted by the user. A

reasoner has the ability to reason about imported ontologies, so for organisational purposes it may be advantageous to class and relationship expressions infer into ontology for organisational purposes. The way that the ontological pattern is realised effects how it can be utilised to enable reasoning, analysis, and reuse of domain knowledge (Trappey et al. 2009).

The OWL API allows users to choose between the FaCt++, HermiT, Pellet and Racer Pro () reasoners. In the prototype system of this research the Pellet reasoner was utilized due to FaCt++ not supporting the unsignedInt data type. This data type is used in the term analyser data property assertions to specify positive scores for the various quality related data properties. The HermiT and Pellet reasoners return easily intelligible error messages when semantic constraints are broken. The Racer Pro reasoner was not tested due to the range of free reasoners being more than adequate. The Pellet and HermiT reasoners both returned the same results during tests. However the HermiT reasoner was more liable to throwing exceptions during retrieval of data types during deployment of the prototype BVA system. The Pellet interface was also more expansive and provided a more concise documentation set.

The OWL DB project is a simple means to store an ontology in a persistence data layer, such as a MySQL database. The benefits of doing this are that the ontology can be periodically backed up. It also opens up the possibility of making a change over a large dataset or slice of a dataset based on a SQL Query. The distinction between OWL/DLs and relational databases is that the former use open-world semantics, whereas the latter use closed-world semantics (Horrocks, Sattler. 2009). Utilising MySQL's relatively powerful backup and storage features should not be seen as infringing on the open world properties of OWL/DLs. It is simply used to backup ontologies periodically.

Class Diagram

The class diagram provides an overall blueprint for the development of a BVA. The main interface, controller, façade and complex queries class concern the main functionality of the system. They provide the user with the means to use the BVA solution and return the corrections and suggestions they need. It is kept completely separated from the maintenance classes that concern allowing administrators to maintain data integrity and the updating of the BVA ontology. The maintenance part of the system would allow an administrator to set up and review scheduled tasks, such as backing up the BVA ontology to a database. Finally the CL classes allow a developer to run a query on the BVA ontology using a command line interface for testing purposes. This would allow a developer to run a test batch script more efficiently than using the main system interface.

The interface layers use the page view controller pattern as this deployment is assumed to be for an enterprise environment that would use the BVA on desktop computers and laptops only. If the deployment was planned for an enterprise that wanted to utilise the BVA on mobiles, PDAs and the MVC pattern would provide a way to manage this additional complexity.

The class diagram utilises the use of single inheritance within the controllers to allow the Main Interface Controller and Maintenance controller to reuse the generalised lower level

methods that the Command Line Controller has. The main reason for this is to reuse the multiple methods that concern the preparation of requests and responses that is generic to all of the controllers, while allowing more specialised methods to be made available to the MI controller and the Maintenance controller. The Façade classes allow the client tier to send and retrieve data in a grouped form. This serves to minimise calls to and from the server minimising network traffic and limiting the possibility of partial dropping of information packets (which could lead to incorrect data being returned or stored). Once on the server the facades relevant independent classes handle the more specific calls to the OWL API, OWL-DB and the Scheduled task Mapper.

Figure 16 BVA Class Diagram

Currently the class diagram demonstrates the system using an ontology outside of a DBMS and a database for backing up the ontologies. The solution could situate a second ontology on a different server which is updated from the backup database periodically, this would be on standby and available in the event of the main ontology server failing. Rangathan & Liu use a standby ontology in a similar fashion in their architecture of Minerva, a scalable, efficient RDBMS based DL reasoner. (Rangathan & Liu. 2006). The class diagram has been used to guide the development of the prototype system, although the prototype system only demonstrates the core functionality.

Ontology

This section documents and critically reflects on the development of the BVA ontology. The central class concept of ontology is that of a term. Multiple individual members of the term

class will make up a terminology. The Term class is further specialised into subclasses, one for each company division in the case study.

Figure 17 Term Classes

This is because the business vocabulary is actually best considered as multiple vocabularies. A vocabulary exists for each division, formed because of their relatively close working environment as well as similarities in work experience and education.

The tangible product term is part of the sales and marketing division’s terminology. It therefore will be represented by the individual object. The term tangible assets should also be considered equivalent to tangible products. It was initially thought that both of these equivalent terms will belong to a plural class to determine the plural rule that applies to them. The problem with this method is that terms with multiple words have complex morphologies to apply a different linguistic form. In this case tangible products become tangible products not tangible products. However, it is not the case with all terms that the last word in a term morphs and none others do.

It was then thought that the plural forms, acronym expansions and gerunds would be treated as individual members within the ontology. After a concept was made in this style it was realised that in the context of the ontology these were not individuals in their own right but information about the individual in question. The next prototype associated word individuals with a term individual and connected with a ‘containsWord’ property. It could then be identified which of the words would need to be pluralised within the individual name. This was undesirable as there was a huge development overhead concerning the modelling of many word individuals. It was also quite complex to follow. The manual development of large ontologies is a huge factor in their realisation. The table below provide examples of the development time of some biomedical, but conceptually similar ontology.

Table 9: No. of classes and effort involved in the production of a number of manually curated ontologies.

Ontology	No. of classes	Subsumption axioms	Duration	Effort in hours
ABO	305	303	3 years	800
Normalisation of CTO	1110	2823	8 months	444
EFO	1420	1873	1 year	1440
InfluenzO	269	223	2.5 years	2900
BioPAX LI	28	67	2.5 years	9900
OBI	1366	2016	3 years	14,296
GO	26894		10 years	> 160 000

Figure 18 manually curated ontologies effort times (Brewster et al. 2009)

The chosen approach uses the much simpler approach of applying data objects for a terms acronym, singular, plural and gerund form. The following figure demonstrates the relationship that term-Tangible_Product has.

Figure 19 Individual relationships for term-Tangible_Product

As Tangible_Product has no gerund or acronym form they are simply not included. OWL axioms, just like dependencies in incomplete databases, do not check the integrity of the database data (Motik et al. 2009).

It was initially thought that the individual would contain the term wording. A naming convention would have to be established for terms so that the proposed systems domain logic can interpret the terms. For example, in the case of spacing words a minus symbol denotes the end of a word. Special characters can be placed after the minus sign to indicate certain rules that need to be applied to the word in that term for a form change. This was undesirable as words with many forms (such as acronym, singular, plural and gerund forms) quickly became difficult to interpret and name accurately. The other downside was that it added a lot of post processing that would have to be done to return the correct term. The revised model uses data relationships on a uniquely named individual which in itself is not returned back to the system. This principled approach makes it possible to accurately specify queries (Welty & Genkins. 1999). Term individuals are represented by their most common non-acronym form.

The initial design used two ontologies, attempting to maximise reuse by encapsulating distinct domains. The BVA ontology encapsulated all the vocabularies terms and the linguistics ontology captured the word rules to organise the terms into relevant form classes. This became difficult to manage and confusing as terms became members of many classes in the linguistics ontology. It was also difficult to categorise a term's morphological form when they contained multiple words. The revised solution uses the BVA ontology to store all asserted information concerning the terms forms and relationships between terms. A key reason for modelling the term forms implicitly is because attempts to infer linguistic rules were problematic as almost none of these were without exception terms and words that break their respective rule. An additional reason is that modelling the terms basic forms is significantly easier for an end user than applying the required linguistics to a term's words to allow it to be inferred into the correct form classes. The Term Analyser

ontology uses class expressions to infer individuals into a meaningful class structure. The Term Tester Ontology uses class expressions to infer individuals into warning classes, which guide the most effective use of the BVA.

The ontology allows for the implicit identification of equivalent terms through the use of symmetric object properties. Terms such as Tangible Products and Tangible Assets can be described by the relationships between them in this way.

Figure 20 inferring an object property through use of the special symmetric type of property

Initially the BVA ontology grouped individuals into multiple classes. In Figure 21 multiple domains and ranges have been picked to ensure that relationship domain and ranges can be applied that only allow acronyms to be associated with expansions.

Figure 21 complex relationship for hasExpansion

This object domain and range relied on an overly complex class hierarchy for Jargon organisation. The follow diagram displays the initial organisation of classes:

Figure 22 Jargon sub classing 1

A problem presented itself once the ontology started to gain complexity from the addition of many more individuals. It becomes unmanageable and a time consuming process to build up even a single term. The next solution reordered the classes to dissect form type before department.

Figure 23 Jargon sub classing 2

This served to remove some of the complexity and confusion presented in Figure 22. However, once the design decision was made to further simplify the class hierarchy by increase use of data properties the final structure looked as follows:

Figure 24 Term Classing with Data Property Assertions

This evolution has demonstrated that Iterative design cycles are an important consideration for ontology development. If the ontology is confusing the overlying domain logic will be harder to develop and as such the solution will be less widely adopted by developers. This is important if development of a solution is to be continued within an online community / open source environment.

Data properties allow individuals to have information stored about them. The information is formalised by the allocation of a data type and given meaning by assigning the relationship a name. In the ontology some terms are considered complex. This means that

as well as other potential transformations (such as an acronym to term expansion) it has been identified as possibly requiring additional information, or for other system implementations perhaps direct replacement. This was initially represented by the `isComplexTerm` data property with data type Boolean. It is assigned a one (true) if it is a complex term and a zero (false) if it is not.

The final solution has the Term Analyser ontology. This uses class expressions to organise terms into further classes to provide additional information about their usage. In this case the use of class expressions allows for terms with explanations to be grouped into the complex term class so that the domain logic layer of the system knows to provide the user with an explanation when it returns an expansion or replacement term. This removes the need to implicitly define the complex term data type, reducing the work load of the user when they need to add new terms. The term analyser ontology uses the domain knowledge asserted in the BVA ontology to infer a range of operational knowledge in the term analyser ontology. Operational knowledge is the diagnostic knowledge; it takes domain knowledge and infers a conclusion, on quality for example (Shue et al. 2009).

Figure 25 the expression for inferring complex terms

In this example a Class Expressions has supplied criteria on a data property. In the term analyser ontology, a complex term is inferred if an analyser term has an explanation string. Class Expressions can also be used to supply criteria for an individual to meet if it is to be inferred into a particular class. They are heavily used in the term analyser ontology. They can be used to express criteria concerning the object property.

Figure 26 the expression for inferring an illegal term

Figure 26 demonstrates how a class expression is used to infer illegal terms.

The Term Tester ontology tests the terms of BVA ontology for invalid and erroneous data. So that the test individuals are not included in the BVA ontology the BVA ontology does not import the TT ontology. However the TT ontology imports the BVA and TA ontology so it can still validate their data.

Figure 27 Import Boundaries of the systems three ontologies

One of the key ways the Term Tester Ontology validates data is by inferring individuals into classes based on cardinality constraints.

Figure 28 the excessive acronym class

A term is put into the excessive acronym class if it has more than five acronyms associated with it. Current online acronym solutions suffer for a lack of accuracy and far too many possibilities are returned. The research by Guo & Zhang suggests that an OWL question and answer ontology, similar in design to this one, could return results with an accuracy of 86% (Guo & Zhang, 2009). It is thought that there is a payoff between accuracy and number of questions that need to be answered. This BVA design only needs to know the department a document has originated from, limiting questions asked to one keeps the solution quick to use. If the solution becomes much larger more questions may need to be asked of the user.

Data range expressions are an effective way to group individuals into classes based on a logical operation

Figure 29 the criteria for an averagely useful term

The concept of this class is to organise terms into classes based on their usage data, interpreted from the domain logic layer of the application.

If further development was to take place it is thought that an additional ontology, the linguistics and syntax predictor ontology could utilise the inference engine for presenting predictions to the user through the interface as they populate a terms forms into the BVA ontology. The difficulty would be dealing with ambiguity during semantic recognition due to the limitations of algorithmic analysis (Kiyavitskaya et al. 2009).

Figure 30 Linguistics and Syntax Predictor Concept

This would speed up the time it took to insert multiple term forms into the BVA ontology by auto completing the word they are typing based on the existing forms. The following section evaluates these findings.

Architecture, Design and Ontology Evaluation (Objective 2)

This section critically assesses the findings of the previous section against the evaluation criteria set out in the Methodology. The primary aim is to assess whether the criteria has been met. It also discusses the implications of meeting the criteria and the limitations of the findings.

The Application

The application findings section aimed to research the use of ontology for a BVA. It was found that the use of ontology gives a developer the ability to infer additional information about individuals and classes, considerably reducing development time, especially if a fit for purpose ontology is available on the internet. It also provides a solution to the difficult issue of handling multiple term forms by managing them efficiently through the use of equivalence and individual relationships. It was found that giving developers a logical and interpretable view of information is important for successful development. Ontology, when viewed with tools such as Protégé provides an easily human interpretable way of organising domain knowledge, allowing developers to quickly understand the concepts within. It also provides an explicit knowledge representation limiting the potential for ambiguous information.

Several future enhancements were identified, which serve to provide evidence that developing a BVA with ontology provides a very extensible solution. Firstly, existing user profile ontology projects could be integrated easily allowing the BVA to deliver individuals a personalised experience. Secondly, for a large scale deployment there is the potential to integrate a linguistics ontology project. Finally, if online content was structured in an organised, descriptive, classifiable and presentable way (Brasethvik & Gulla, 2001) the BVA ontology could be adapted for integration with the semantic web, allowing a richer information experience when visiting websites and easier retrieval of relevant information.

Architecture and Design

The findings architecture and design section looked at how a BVA system could be realised. This section uses the prototype system implementation to assist with gauging the merits of the architecture and design. Initially the requirements of the BVA were defined, it was ascertained that design specific requirements differ from architectural level requirements and guidance into creating design specific requirements was demonstrated. A high level architecture critically analysed the high level deployment considerations and it was found that a client / server tier approach which utilised a three layer architecture was most suitable.

As identified as a requirement in objective one, an in-depth analysis into the UI design of a BVA was undertaken. It provided examples of possible future deployments as well as developed deployment examples from the prototype. The need for different UI views for different staff was realised and a query input was defined. The use of the OWL-API was justified, through research and demonstration of the deployed prototype system. The use of reasoners was discussed and it was decided that the best reasoner to use was the pellet reasoner. Maintenance issues and the use of OWL DB to periodically backup the ontology were researched. Finally a BVA class diagram was developed which incorporates a lot of the findings earlier in the chapter. Elements of this class diagram were used to guide the development of the prototype system; as the development of the solution was a success, this serves as verification of the results drawn in this part of the research. (Shaw, 2001)

Ontology

The following section concisely evaluates the findings of the ontology section. It was thought that ontology is a very iterative process, taking many iteration cycles before the final design was realised. Ontology building requires not only an intimate and comprehensive understanding of a domain, but the commitment of substantial amounts of time in its conceptual exploration (Culley, Darlington. 2008). The use of term classes to organise multiple business vocabularies was made to allow terms to be associated with one of more vocabularies. Through experimentation was made in arriving at the solution of using a data property hierarchy for individual term linguistics. This significance of this decision was reiterated during prototype system deployment, as this method was well suited to being queried. The use of three ontologies, but only one of which requires asserted information should reduce maintenance significantly. The use of class expressions in the analysing and testing ontologies allows the other two to be populated and provide the BVA with additional information primarily for the maintenance of a system. The uses of

prediction, linguistics and profile ontologies to create an easy to maintain and better user experience were identified as future enhancements.

Scenario Testing

This section looks at how the BVA prototype system (the development of which was guided by the architecture and utilises the developed ontology) performs in three demonstrative scenarios. It should firmly demonstrate that the three types of problematic terms discovered by the research can be handled.

The first scenario utilises the dictionary style term finder to demonstrate how an employee could look up an unknown term, PIIPs, discovered in an email from the engineering department. The second scenario is more complex, demonstrating the use of the test analyser to uncover the meaning of a sentence containing an acronym and a slang term. The final scenario utilises the text analyser again to uncover the meanings of many acronyms, complex terms and slang terms. The scenarios can be executed on the prototype application by visiting www.owl-bva.appspot.com.

Figure 31 Scenario one - Returning a acronym meaning

Figure 32 Scenario 2 - returning slang and acronym meanings from a sentence

Figure 33 Returning Slang, Acronym and Complex Term meanings from a passage of text

The scenarios present the use of two types of BVA implementation which demonstrates that the architecture, design and ontology can be used to develop an application which can

meet the fundamental requirements of the developed system. The concluding section reflects on the research as a whole and discusses future work and enhancements.

Conclusions

This concluding section reflects on the research as a whole. The research initially identified the types of terminology that cause employees difficulty when interpreting written documentation. This has been achieved by interviewing, analysing documentation originating from within enterprises and reviewing relevant journal articles within the field. The outcome of this initial research stage identified three ways the BVA should assist employees by:

- Expanding acronyms based on their origins; different departments can use the same acronym for a different expanded terminology.
- Enforcing the use of an agreed business vocabulary by providing the author with synonyms for slang, misleading or non-words.
- Adding an explanation to complex terms which may not be understood outside their department of origin.

This is a significant finding as it sets out the fundamental requirements for any future BVA work to be carried out. This theory was then further confirmed through the testing of 49 subjects. It was found that providing additional information to complex, abbreviated and business area specific terminology improves the understanding of written documentation across a wide range of age groups, level of industry experience and academic excellence.

A highly appropriate architecture has been proposed through substantial analysis of many academically and industrially recognised patterns and architectural designs. Potential technologies for adoption into a BVA have been identified by actively experimenting with their functionality and critically analysing their suitability. The deployment considerations which would guide the successful deployment of a BVA have been critically evaluated. The identified solution for industrial adoption of a BVA solution would involve developing the interface code to act as a plug-in to a popular word processing suite, in a similar way to a spell checker or thesaurus. The large-scale realisation of a BVA may require additional research into utilising a DBMS system while retaining the open world characteristics and reasoner capabilities of ontology. This is due to the poor capability of current ontology techniques to handle very large ontologies, in particular regarding scalability of reasoners (Al-Jadir et al. 2010). The current BVA prototype did not integrate into a word processing suite and instead is implemented in a client / server approach. It utilises some of the architecture and designs class diagrams. A planned future task is to develop the application to meet the specification of the full class diagram and utilise MVC and APIs to provide mobile BVA checkers and word processor plug-ins.

Multiple potential ontology designs have been developed and critically evaluated and a final design has been developed. Its ability to provide a complete solution for users dealing with complex, abbreviated and business area specific terminology has been demonstrated

through querying the ontology and evaluating the output. In addition to this the ontology and architecture and design have been proven by the BVA prototype system, which is important as it proves the architecture and design can be utilised for future BVA implementations. The advantage of the ontology approach has been evaluated. It is suggested that, in terms of the effort involved, populating the ontology could be realised by deploying the BVA as an online project as ontology promotes collaborative online efforts to grow ontologies in a way that maximises reuse. Tools to assist ontology reuse currently perform very specific tasks and it is a fairly manual process. As more industrial adopters appear the availability, functionality, scalability and performance of technologies are likely to improve rapidly (Simperl. 2009). This would ultimately assist the deployment of a BVA solution. Future enhancements such as the prediction ontology have been identified which act to further reduce the time to develop a large scale BVA ontology, which has been identified as a major consideration to successful BVA deployment.

References

- Al-Jadir, L. Parent, C. Spaccapietra, S., 2010. Reasoning with large ontologies stored in relational databases: The OntoMinD approach. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*. 69(11) pp. 1158-1180
- Bada, M. Hunter, L., 2010. Desiderata for ontologies to be used in semantic annotation of biomedical documents. *Journal of Biomedical informatics*. 44(1) pp. 94-101
- Balan, S., Punithavalli, M., 2010, Software-Architecture for Object Oriented Systems-Usability Patterns. *IJCSNS*, 10 (10) pp. 50-65
- Battle, R. Benson, E., 2007. Bridging the semantic web and web 2.0 with representational state transfer (REST). *Journal of Web Semantics*. 6(1) pp. 61-60
-
- Bellatreche, L. Dung, N,X. Pierra, G. Hondjack, D., 2006. Contribution of ontology-based data modelling to automatic integration of electronic catalogues within engineering databases. *Computers in industry*. 57(8-9) pp.711-724.
- Blair, R, C., 1960. A Program for Correcting Spelling Errors.* *Information and Control*.* 3(1) pp. 60-67
- Bobillo, F. Delgado, M. Gomez-Romero, J. Lopex, E., 2009. A semantic fuzzy expert system for a fuzzy balanced scorecard. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 36(1) pp. 423-433.
- Bosch, J., 2004. Software Architecture: The Next Step. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. 3047(1), pp. 194-199
- Brasethvik, T, Gulla, J, A., 2001. Natural language analysis for semantic document modelling, *Data & Knowledge Engineering*. 38(1), pp. 45-62

- Brennan, P, F. Aronson A, R., 2003. Towards linking patients and clinical information: detecting UMLS concepts in e-mail. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*. 36(4-5) pp.334-341
- Brewster, C. Jupp, S. Luciano, J. Shotton, D. Stevens, R, D. Issues in learning an ontology from text. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 2009, 10(5) pp. 1-20
- Broekstra, J. Klein, M. Decker, S. Fensel, D. Harmelen, F. Horrocks, I., 2002. Enabling knowledge representation on the Web by extending RDF. *Computer Networks*, 39 (5) pp. 609-634
- Culley, S.J. Darlington, M,J., 2008. Investigating ontology development for engineering design support. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*. 22(1) pp. 112-134.
- Cranefield, S. Pan, J. 2007. Bridging the gap between the model-driven architecture and ontology engineering. *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*. 65(7) pp.595-609.
- Dill, S. Eiron, N. Gibson, D. Gruhl, D. Guha, R. Jhingran, A. Kanungo, T. McCurley, K, S. Rajagopalan, S. Tomkins, A. Tomlin, J, A. Zien, J, Y., 2003. A case for automated large-scale semantic annotation, *Journal of Web Semantics* 1 (1). 115–132.
- Djurić, D. Gašević, D. Devedžić, V., 2005. Ontology Modeling and MDA. *Journal of Object Technology*. 4(1). pp. 109-128.
- Eriksson, H., 2007. The semantic-document approach to combining documents and ontologies. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*. 65(7) pp. 140-160
- Fowler, M., 2003, *Patterns of application architecture*. Boston, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Fu, R. Yue, X. Song, M. Xin, Z., 2008. An architecture of knowledge management system based on agent and ontology. *The Journal of China Universities of Posts and Telecommunications*. 16(4) pp. 126-130.
- García-Sánchez, F. Valencia-García, R. Martínez-Béjar, R. Fernández-Breis, J,T., 2009. An ontology, intelligent agent-based framework for the provision of semantic web services. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 36(2) pp. 3167-3187.
- Gold Community, 2010. Gold Versions. [online] <<http://linguistics-ontology.org/version>> [Accessed 09/07/2011]
- Guo, Q. Zhang, M., 2009. Semantic information integration and question answering based on pervasive agent ontology. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 63(1) pp. 63-75.
- Gray, A. Gray, N. Hall, C, W. Ounis, I., Finding the right term: Retrieving and exploring semantic concepts in astronomical vocabularies. *Information Processing & Management*. 46(4) pp. 470-478
- Gruber, T., 1993. A translation approach to portable ontology specifications, *Knowledge Acquisition*. 5(2) pp. 199-220

- Haswell, R., 2005. Automated Text-checkers: A Chronology and a Bibliography of Commentary. *Computers and Composition Online*. [e-Journal]. Available at: <<http://www.bgsu.edu/cconline/prodev>>. [Accessed 16 July 2011]
- Hevner, A, R. March, S, T. Park, J. Ram, S., 2004 Design Science in Information Systems Research. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*. 28(1) pp. 75-105
- Jurisica, I. Mylopoulos, J. Yu, E., 2004. Ontologies for Knowledge Management: An Information Systems Perspective. *Knowledge and Information systems* 6(4) pp. 380-401
- Kang, D. Lee, J. Choi, S. Kim, K., 2010. An ontology-based Enterprise Architecture. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 37(2) pp. 1456-1464.
- Kiyavitskaya , N. Zeni, N. Cordy, J, R. Mich, L. Mylopoulos, J. 2009. Cerno: Light-weight tool support for semantic annotation of textual documents. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*, 68 (12), pp. 1470-1492
- Ludewig, J., 2003. Models in software engineering – an introduction. *Software and Systems Modelling*, 2(1), pp.5-14.
- Ma, X. Wu, C. Carranza, E, J. Schetselaar, E, M. Meer, F. Liu, G. Wang, X. Zhang, X. 2010. Development of a controlled vocabulary for semantic interoperability of mineral exploration geodata for mining projects. *Computers & Geosciences*, 36(12) December 2010, pp. 1512-1522
- March, S, T. Smith, G, F., 1995. Design and natural science research on information technology. *Decision Support Systems*. 15(4) pp. 251-266
- Motik, B. Horrocks, I. Sattler, U., 2009. Bridging the gap between OWL and relational databases. *Web Semantics: Science and Agents on the World Wide Web*. 7(2) pp. 74-89.
- Nesic, S. Gasevic, D. Jazayeri, M., 2008. Semantic Document Management for Collaborative Learning Object Authoring. ICALT '08. Eighth IEEE International Conference on pp. 751-755
- Peffer, K. Tuure, T. Rothenberger, M, A. Samir, C., 2008 A Design Science Research Methodology for Information Systems Research. *Journal of Management Information Systems*. 24(3) pp.45-77
- Princeton University, 2011. WordNet: A lexical database for English. [online] available at: <<http://wordnet.princeton.edu/>> [Accessed 02/07/2011]
- Ranganathan, A. Liu, Z. 2006. Information Retrieval from Relational Database using Semantic Queries. *CIKM '06 Proceedings of the 15th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management*. Arlington, USA, 5 November, New York, USA: ACM.
- Shaw, M., 2001. The Coming-of-Age of Software Architecture Research. *Institute for Software Research, Proceedings of the 23rd international conference on Software Engineering*. Pittsburgh: Carnegie Mellon University.

Shue, L.Y. Chen, C.W. Shiue, W., 2009. The development of an ontology-based expert system for corporate financial rating. *Expert Systems with Applications*. 36(2) pp.2130-2142.

Simperl, E., 2009. Reusing ontologies on the semantic web: A feasibility study. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*. 68(10) pp.905-925

Stanford University, 2009. *Protégé 4 announcement*. [online] available at: <http://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/P4_Release_Announcement> [Accessed 04/06/2011]

Trappey, A. J. C. Trappey, C. V. Wu, C., 2009. Automatic patent document summarization for collaborative knowledge systems and services *Journal of Systems Science and Systems Engineering*. 18 (1) pp. 71-94

ViziQuer, 2010. ViziQuer. [online] available at: <<http://viziquer.lumii.lv/>> [Accessed 24/06/2010]

W3C, 2009. *OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Document Overview*. [online] available at: <<http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>> [Accessed 05/06/2011]

Welty, C. A. Jenkins, J., 1999. Formal ontology for subject. *Data & knowledge Engineering*. 31(2) pp. 155-181

Yang, D. Miao, R. Zhou, Y., 2009. Product configuration knowledge modelling using ontology web language *Expert Systems with Applications*. 36(3 Part 1) pp. 4399-4411